

An intelligent healthcare currency can reduce cost of healthcare administration and cut fraud, waste and abuse

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Healthcare payments are very challenging due to 3rd party model, involvement of multiple stakeholders and complexity of transactions. It is not unusual for the payment administration to cost as much as the payment for services. There is no other industry with a comparable cost and complexity of payments at this scale. The systems and processes used to administer healthcare payments focus on making sure each transaction is accurate while trying to deal with retroactive events, and it is a losing battle.

2. Aim

Make healthcare and benefit programs work better for everyone: for ourselves, parents, children, society and our economy. Build a community of developers, partners and resellers to continually expand the platform and apply collective intelligence

3. Material and methods

We will discuss how an intelligent currency built on Blockchain and smart contracts can be used to make healthcare payments efficient, transparent, accountable, auditable and adjustable.

We will present a currency design and approach that can replace complex payment systems with a programmable healthcare currency that will cost a fraction of current payment models, significantly reduce fraud and abuse and lead to more effective delivery and use of care.

4. Results

Solve.Care leadership team has decades of experience in building complex IT systems to serve healthcare delivery and administration. The team is combining Blockchain technology, domain expertise and public policy experience to redefine healthcare administration in the US and around the world.

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5. Conclusions

We will be presenting our past research on healthcare costs and inefficiency and specific use cases and applications that can transform government programs, employee benefit administration and care coordination for all.

6. Keywords

Blockchain, Healthcare, Smart-Contracts.

Author biography

Pradeep Goel Pradeep Goel arrived from India 23 years ago to study in America. And now he is CEO of a fast-growing technology company. Mr. Goel was deeply involved in designing and building solutions for several public programs such as Medicaid, Children health insurance, Medicare, SNAP, TANF, mental health and many others. He has worked for and with insurance companies, employer sponsored benefits and US government programs related to healthcare, benefits and financial administration. Throughout his career, Pradeep has championed product management, sustainable design and architecture, and usability in enterprise and government systems. In 2017 Pradeep Goel had Launched Solve.Care as the first decentralize benefit administration platform, protocol and currency to revolutionize health and social benefit administration in the US and worldwide.